

MODELING THE FIRE STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE OF ALUMINUM AND REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Aluminum alloys and glass fibre epoxy laminates are often used as light-weight structural materials due to a good combination of high specific stiffness and strength. When combined to create hybrid fibre/polymer/aluminum composites such as Glass Laminate Aluminum Reinforced Epoxy (GLARE) composites, mechanical properties are further enhanced. However, a problem with using aluminum alloys in structural applications where fire is an ever present risk, such as aircraft, ships, buildings and oil drilling platforms, is their susceptibility to softening at moderately low temperatures. Aluminum alloys experience large reductions to their elastic stiffness, proof strength, ultimate strength and creep strength when heated beyond the range 100 to 400°C [1,2], which is well below the flaming temperature of typical fires. As a result, aluminum-based structures can distort, buckle and collapse within a short time when exposed to a hot fire.

Similarly, a major problem with using fibre reinforced polymer composites in structural engineering applications is their susceptibility to softening, thermal degradation and thermal decomposition leading to failure in the event of fire. Most polymer matrix systems soften at elevated temperatures ($80^{\circ}\text{C} < T < 200^{\circ}\text{C}$) due to their inherently low glass transition temperatures. When exposed at high temperatures such as those created by fire ($T > 300^{\circ}\text{C}$), fibre/polymer composites decompose into volatiles and/or char. It has been demonstrated that the structural survivability of composite engineering structures relies on the composite resisting deformation and failure, rather than on the avoidance of flaming combustion [3]. Thus, the thermal softening of the polymer matrix is the dominant process controlling the structural behavior of fibre/polymer composites in high

temperature and fire environments. At elevated and high temperatures, the degradation of the polymer leads to inefficient stress transfer between the matrix and fibres hence structural property deterioration.

When used in GLARE, the relatively low softening temperatures coupled with comparatively short burn through times for aluminum alloys and the inherent flammability of fibre/polymer laminates necessitates a requirement for these hybrid composites to pass stringent fire tests before they can be incorporated into fire-prone engineering structures. However, the experimental qualification of varied configurations and geometries of hybrid fibre/polymer/aluminum composites is labor-intensive and costly. The development of analytical or numerical models that can be used to predict the fire structural performance of hybrid fibre/polymer/aluminum composites such as GLARE is a research area of interest.

The authors are currently developing predictive models for the fire structural performance of GLARE composites. As part of this exercise, it is critical to understand fire structural behaviors of materials that constitute GLARE namely fibre/polymer laminates and aluminum alloys. In this paper, the thermo-mechanical behaviors of a select aluminum alloy (5083-H116) and E-glass/vinyl ester (GVE) composite laminate system were independently characterized via experimental testing with the data used to validate the predictive fire structural models.

2 Thermal and Fire Structural Modeling

2.1 Thermal Modeling of Aluminum

The modeling approach considers an aluminum plate subjected to axial compression loading and one-sided transient heating by fire. The temperature through the plate is calculated using heat conduction

theory:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[k_x(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[k_y(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left[k_z(T) \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right] \quad [1]$$

where ρ is the density of aluminum. The subscripts: x , y and z , refer to the through-thickness, in-plane and transverse directions of the plate. The thermal conductivity, k (which is dependent on the alloy series) is related to temperature according to [4]:

$$k = 0.07T + 190 \text{ (W/m}^\circ\text{C);} \quad [2]$$

(for 1xxx, 3xxx, 6xxx alloys); and,

$$k = 0.1T + 140 \text{ (W/m}^\circ\text{C)} \quad [3]$$

(for 2xxx, 4xxx, 5xxx, 7xxx alloys)

The alloy series-independent specific heat, C_p , of aluminum increases linearly with temperature [4]:

$$C_p = 0.41T + 903 \text{ (J/kg}^\circ\text{C)} \quad [4]$$

The thermal boundary condition at the fire exposed surface is specified by the heat flux (q''):

$$-k \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} = q''_{s,0} \quad [5]$$

The net heat flux (radiant and convective) at the fire exposed aluminum surface is calculated by:

$$q''_{s,0} = \varepsilon (q''_{rad} - \sigma T_s^4) + h_{conv} (T_{\infty,0} - T_s) \quad [6]$$

where q''_{rad} is the radiant incident heat flux from the fire; ε is the emissivity of aluminum; h_{conv} is the convective heat enthalpy; T_s is the fire-exposed surface temperature of the aluminum plate; and T_{∞} is the reference temperature (usually 20°C).

The boundary condition on the unexposed side of the aluminum is also assumed to consist of convective and radiant components:

$$q''_{s,L} = \varepsilon \sigma_{SB} (T_s^4 - T_{\infty,L}^4) + h_{conv} (T_s - T_{\infty,L}) \quad [7]$$

where σ_{SB} is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant.

Using this thermal analysis, it is possible to calculate the temperature at any location in an aluminum plate when exposed to transient heating conditions.

2.2 Structural Modeling of Aluminum

The structural response of an aluminum plate under combined compression loading and one-sided heating by fire is determined mainly by the reduction in the time-independent mechanical properties (Young's modulus, yield stress) for short failure times, which involves high applied loads and temperatures. The temperature at which creep effects become important is generally considered to be half the melting temperature of aluminum. Modeling the fire structural response of aluminum for loading and temperature conditions that result in relatively long times-to-failure (typically above several minutes and temperatures above 170°C) therefore requires time-dependent creep analysis.

Maljaars et al. [1] developed a creep-based model to predict the critical temperature for the onset of failure of compression-loaded aluminum sections exposed to fire. They showed that this temperature corresponds to a critical creep strain, at which point the aluminum will begin to fail by plastic buckling. A similar approach is used in this paper for analyzing the fire structural response of aluminum.

The total in-plane compressive strain (ε) in aluminum when exposed to combined elastic compression loading and one-sided heating by fire is the sum of the mechanical elastic strain (ε_{el}) and creep strain (ε_c) less the tensile strain caused by thermal expansion (ε_α):

$$\varepsilon(t, T) = \varepsilon_{el}(T) + \varepsilon_c(t, T) - \varepsilon_\alpha(t, T) \quad [8]$$

where the time-independent elastic strain is simply determined by:

$$\varepsilon_{el}(T) = \frac{\sigma}{E(T)} \quad [9]$$

where σ is the applied elastic stress and E is the Young's modulus which is a function of temperature. The thermal expansion tensile strain is calculated by:

$$\varepsilon_{\alpha}(t, T) = \alpha(T - T_{\infty}) \quad [10]$$

where the temperature (T) is time-dependent due to the transient thermal nature of fires and α is the thermal expansion coefficient for aluminum:

$$\alpha = 10^{-9}T^2 + 22.5 \times 10^{-6}T - 4.5 \times 10^{-4} \quad [11]$$

Several models exist to calculate creep strain, ε_c [5-7], and used here is the Dorn-Harmathy creep model [8] which predicts the strain during the primary and secondary creep stages:

$$\varepsilon_{c,I+II}(t) = \dot{\varepsilon}_{II} \coth^2 \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{c,I+II}}{\varepsilon_{c,0}} \right) \quad [12]$$

The tertiary creep stage is not considered in the analysis because the aluminum under compression loading does not fail by creep-induced rupture. In Eqn. 12, $\varepsilon_{c,0}$ is the projection back to zero time of the secondary creep strain curve and $\dot{\varepsilon}_{II}$ is the steady-state strain rate during the secondary creep stage, which depends on the applied stress and temperature. The effects of applied stress and temperature during secondary creep are analyzed using an Arrhenius-type relationship:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{II} = A_{II} \sigma_c^{n_{II}} e^{(-Q_{II}/RT)} \quad [13]$$

where A_{II} is a pre-exponential material parameter for secondary creep; n_{II} is the fitted secondary creep exponent; Q_{II} is the creep activation energy; and R is the Boltzmann constant. T is the absolute temperature, which is calculated using the transient thermal analysis described above (equations 1-7).

The creep strain at zero time, $\varepsilon_{c,0}$, is considered by Maljaars et al. [1] to depend on stress only. However, $\varepsilon_{c,0}$ is actually a function of both stress and temperature, and the creep parameters must be calculated using a stress-temperature decoupling approach similar to that defined for the secondary creep strain rate in Eqn. 13:

$$\varepsilon_{c,0} = A_I \sigma_c^{n_I} e^{(-Q_I/RT)} \quad [14]$$

where A_I is a material parameter for primary creep; n_I is the material exponent for primary creep; and Q_I is the activation energy for primary creep. The creep parameters of the material must be determined by creep testing.

The creep strain history of aluminum under compression loading can be calculated by iteratively solving Eqn. 12 for increasing temperature and time for the transient heating conditions of fire. The model predicts an asymptotic increase in strain caused by excessive creep softening when the applied stress and fire temperature conditions exceed the critical limit. This creep softening induces a mechanical instability that causes the aluminum plate to failure by buckling.

In the modeling, the creep strain at which failure is observed must be calibrated with one experimental condition. This creep strain value is sensitive to several variables, most notably the presence of imperfections in the aluminum plate (particularly out-of-plane waviness from sheet forming) as well as the loading and thermal boundary conditions. (The calibration conditions used in this study were a heat flux of 35 kW/m² and an applied stress of 50 MPa, although any heat flux and stress level would be suitable for calibration). The modeling approach predicts the critical temperature and time for the onset of excessive creep softening that leads to buckling failure of compression-loaded aluminum exposed to fire.

2.3 Thermal Modeling of GVE Composites

A 1D heat transfer model was used to calculate the temperature rise in the through-thickness direction of the GVE laminate due to heat flow into the composite material from the radiant heater. This model was originally developed by Henderson et al. [9, 10] and later modified by Gibson et al. [11]. The analysis has been described in numerous papers [12-20] and therefore is only briefly explained here. The 1D governing equation for the laminate substrate is expressed as:

$$\left[\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right] \rho_c C_{p,c} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\lambda_c \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right] - \dot{m}_G C_{p,g} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - (Q_c + h_c - h_g) \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \quad [15]$$

The first term on the right hand-side represents heat conduction into the laminate from the radiant heater.

The second term describes the mass flow of volatile products generated by decomposition of the polymer matrix into the atmosphere. A third term analyses the heat absorbed during thermal decomposition of the polymer matrix, which is assumed to be an endothermic reaction process. The fibres are considered to be thermally inert at the exposure temperatures investigated.

The temperature profile through-the-thickness of the laminate and the extent of thermal degradation of the polymer matrix are calculated using the thermal model described by Eqn. 15. During thermal decomposition of the polymer matrix, the phase states present within the laminate are the fully decomposed (char) phase represented by the mass fraction, f_{char} , and the virgin (un-decomposed) phase represented by the mass fraction, f_{virgin} . Assuming that there is no significant change in the volume of the laminate due to this phase change, the instantaneous mass fraction of solid material present at any time in relation to the original mass of virgin material can be calculated using:

$$f = \frac{\rho - \rho_{char}}{\rho_{virgin} - \rho_{char}} \quad [16]$$

If the mass density is assumed to follow rule-of-mixtures, then:

$$f = f_{virgin}(\rho_{virgin}) + f_{char}(\rho_{char}) \quad [17]$$

The thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of the laminates are respectively calculated using:

$$\lambda_c(T) = f_{virgin}\lambda_{virgin}(T) + f_{char}\lambda_{char}(T) \quad [18]$$

$$C_p(T) = f_{virgin}C_{P,virgin}(T) + f_{char}C_{P,char}(T) \quad [19]$$

where the first term on the right hand side of equations 18 and 19 represents the contribution from the virgin phase while the second term represents the contribution from the char phase.

Matrix decomposition is assumed to follow a single-stage Arrhenius rate equation of the form:

$$\left[\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t}\right] = -(\rho_{virgin} - \rho_{char}) \left[\frac{\rho - \rho_{char}}{\rho_{virgin} - \rho_{char}}\right]^n \cdot A_c e^{-E_a/RT} \quad [20]$$

The order of reaction, n , is assigned a value of unity in this study; i.e. decomposition follows first-order reaction kinetics. Mass-loss kinetic (Arrhenius) parameters are determined from TGA data.

2.4 Structural Modeling of GVE Composites

The temperature profile in the through-thickness direction of the laminate as a function of exposure time to the fire is calculated first. This is then followed by the second and final step of calculating the strength and failure under axial compression loading. Various mechanical models can be applied in this step to calculate the load response of the hot laminate [12, 13], although in this study the average strength-based analysis by Feih et al. [14-16] is used. Feih and colleagues developed a strength-based model that can be applied to a laminate under combined one-sided heating and static compression [14] or tension [15] loading to predict softening and failure. The analysis involved with these models is described in detail elsewhere [14, 15], and therefore is only briefly outlined here.

In the analysis of a hot, decomposing laminate under compression loading, Feih et al. [14] assume that the reduction in compressive strength in the through-the-thickness direction due to thermal softening and decomposition is dependent on the temperature profile. The analysis involves determining the local strength at many locations through the laminate based on the local temperature. At any location in the laminate, the local strength is related to the local temperature by:

$$\sigma_c(T) = \left(\frac{\sigma_{C(0)} + \sigma_{C(R)}}{2} - \frac{\sigma_{C(0)} - \sigma_{C(R)}}{2} \tanh(\Phi(T - T_{0.5})) \right) R_{rc}(T)^n \quad [21]$$

The first term on right-hand considers thermal softening of the laminate, which is assumed to occur over as a single-stage brittle-to-rubbery phase transformation of the polymer matrix. The parameters - $\sigma_{C(0)}$, $\sigma_{C(R)}$, Φ , $T_{0.5}$ - must be measured or derived from isothermal compressive strength tests on the laminate over the temperature range of interest. The second term considers further depletion

due to matrix decomposition, where the term R_{rc} is the residual mass fraction of polymer in the decomposing laminate. The exponent n' to $R_{rc}(T)$ is dependent on the relationship between polymer decomposition and residual strength, and is assumed to equal 3. R_{rc} is calculated using Eqn. 20 based on changes in material density due to decomposition.

After the local compressive strengths have been calculated at a number of locations through the laminate, the bulk (average) compressive strength is determined using the Simpson integration technique:

$$\sigma_{av} = \frac{1}{h} \int_0^h \sigma(x) dx \quad [22]$$

where:

$$\int_0^h \sigma(x) dx = \frac{h}{3b} [\sigma(x_0) + 4\sigma(x_1) + 2\sigma(x_2) + \dots + 2\sigma(x_{y-2}) + 4\sigma(x_{y-1}) + \sigma(x_y)] \quad [23]$$

In Eqn. 23, b defines an even number of locations where the local compressive strength values are calculated, and was set at 50 in this study. Equation 22 is solved for increasing increments of time to calculate the reduction in the average compressive strength of the laminate substrate with increasing exposure time to fire. The time-to-failure is calculated using the fire exposure time needed for the average strength of the laminate to reduce to the applied compressive stress. This failure criterion assumes that at this point all the ply layers in the laminate fail in compression at the same time.

3 Experimental

3.1 Materials and Experimental Methods

A 5xxx aluminium alloy (5083-H116; China Steel) was used to validate the modelling approach. This is a non-age-hardenable alloy with the following mechanical properties at room temperature: Young's modulus (70 GPa), proof strength (260 MPa) and ultimate strength (360 MPa). Test specimens were cut from rolled 5083 sheet, with the specimen axis parallel to the rolling direction.

Glass-vinyl ester laminates were used to validate the model. The laminates were fabricated from plain woven E-glass fabric (800 g/m²) and vinyl ester resin (Derakane 411-350; Ashland Composite Polymers). The laminates were produced using the

vacuum bag resin infusion process, and then cured under ambient conditions (20°C, 55% RH) followed by an elevated temperature post-cure (80°C for 2 h). The laminates had a fibre volume fraction of 55%.

3.2 High Temperature Static Testing: Aluminum

Tensile tests were performed on the 5083 Al under iso-thermal conditions over the temperature range of 25-400°C to determine the softening of the elastic modulus and proof strength. The tensile specimens were dog-bone shaped coupons with a necked gauge section of 8.0 mm wide, 10.2 mm thick and 600 mm long. The specimens were loaded in tension according to ASTM B557 specifications. The specimens were centrally heated over a 100 mm section of the gauge region using a temperature-controllable heating device. This device prevented heating of the grips and load cell of the tension machine (100 kN MTS). Specimens were allowed to equilibrate at the test temperature prior to loading at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min.

Iso-thermal creep tests were performed on the aluminum using the same dog-bone shape specimen as used for the tension tests. The specimens were held at zero stress at the creep test temperature until they reached thermal equilibrium, and were then loaded to the creep test stress. Creep tests were performed at constant temperatures between 300 and 400°C and constant stress levels between 50 and 90 MPa. Material parameters describing the primary and secondary creep stages were determined.

Transient state creep tests were carried out using a similar methodology to the static creep tests. The aluminum was loaded to a constant elastic stress (50 MPa) while the temperature was increased at a controlled rate of 12°C/min until rupture. The test results were used to validate the creep material parameters derived from isothermal creep tests for transient thermal conditions for creep.

3.3 Fire Structural Testing: Aluminum

Rectangular aluminum specimens were loaded axially in compression while being heated from one side using an electric radiant heater as shown in Figure 1. The specimens were 50 mm wide, 10.2 mm thick, and 470 mm long; although only 100 mm of the mid-section was exposed to the heater while the rest of the specimen was thermally insulated.

The distance between the heater and specimen was 25 mm. The specimens were coated with heat resistant black paint to achieve high thermal emissivity of 0.9.

Figure 1: Schematic of the fire structural test set-up for aluminum plates or GVE composites.

While under load, the specimens were exposed to constant incident heat fluxes (35 or 50 kW/m²) using a 500 W conical radiant heater which heated the center of the specimen to maximum temperatures of about 280 and 360°C, respectively. The temperature profiles as a function of exposure time are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Temperature profiles measured at the center (i.e. one-half of the specimen length) of the aluminum test specimen as a function of exposure time for heat fluxes of 35 and 50 kW/m².

A constant compression load was applied to the specimens using a 250 kN MTS machine at between 10 and 90% of the Euler buckling stress at 20°C (105 MPa) while being exposed to radiant heat. Axial and out-of-plane deformations of the specimen due to thermal expansion and buckling were measured. Out-of-plane displacements were measured using a linear variable differential transformer (LVDT). The LVDT probe is made out of a ceramic material in order to prevent measurement errors due to thermal expansion when in contact with the heated specimen. LVDT measurements were used to define the initiation of failure, which corresponded with the start of irreversible in-plane and out-of-plane deflections of the aluminum test article due to plastic buckling. The time and temperature at which this deflection instability commenced was taken to define failure initiation. The time and temperature when the specimen collapsed due to excessive softening and distortion were also measured.

3.4 Fire Structural Testing: GVE Composites

The fire structural tests on GVE laminates (600 mm long, 50 mm wide and 10 mm thick) were conducted using the same fixture described for aluminum plates. The specimens were insulated with an inert ceramic fibre material (Fibrefrax® 550K) except for a 100 mm section at the center, which was exposed directly to the heat source. A 500 W conical radiant heater operated at an incident heat flux of 50 kW/m² was used as the heat source. The heat source was located 25 mm from the test specimen, and both were aligned in the vertical orientation. While exposed to the heat source, the specimens were loaded to a constant compressive stress using a 250 kN MTS machine fitted with a smoke exhaust system. Specimens were tested at different compressive load levels between 10 and 90% of the buckling stress at room temperature (21 MPa). The time the specimen can sustain the combined heating and applied load is the failure time and was used to validate the model. Two specimens were tested for each fire structural condition. Further details on this fire structural test method are given by Feih et al. [14-16]. Temperature measurements were taken during testing at the exposed surface, mid-thickness of the laminate, and the unexposed laminate surface using K-type thermocouples.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Fire Structural Response: Aluminum

The creep-based model to analyze the structural response of aluminum to fire requires creep property data. Creep strain-time curves measured for the 5083 Al alloy under different temperature and stress conditions are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Creep curves at (a) different stress levels at constant temperature of 350°C and (b) different temperatures at constant stress load of 50 MPa.

The steady-state creep strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_{II}$) was determined from these curves, and its natural logarithm is plotted against the reciprocal of absolute temperature or the natural logarithm of compressive stress in Figure 4 to calculate the activation energy ($Q_{II} = 1.23 \times 10^5$ J/mol), exponent ($n_{II} = 5.05 \text{ MPa}^{(-5.05)}$), and pre-exponential factor ($A_{II} = 0.0027 \text{ s}^{-1}$) for secondary creep. These parameters are used in solving the creep model.

Figure 4: Plots of (a) $\ln \dot{\epsilon}_{II}$ versus $1/T$ for constant stress; 50 MPa and (b) $\ln \dot{\epsilon}_{II}$ versus $\ln \sigma_c$ at 350 °C.

The model requires the creep strain value at zero time ($\epsilon_{c,0}$), which must also be experimentally determined. Like $\dot{\epsilon}_{II}$, $\epsilon_{c,0}$ is a function of both stress and temperature, and parameters describing this relationship are calculated using a stress-temperature decoupling procedure. A plot of $\ln \epsilon_{c,0}$ against $\ln \sigma_c$ (Figure 5) yields a slope, n_I , which is equivalent to $-4.16 \text{ MPa}^{(4.16)}$. $\ln \epsilon_{c,0}$ is plotted against the reciprocal of absolute temperature in Figure 5 to calculate the apparent activation energy for primary creep ($Q_I = 2.83 \times 10^4$ J/mol). A 3D fitting procedure utilizing the experimental stress-temperature dependent creep strain at zero time and a curve fitting minimization algorithm were used to calculate $A_I = 1.81 \times 10^8$.

Figure 5: Plots of (a) $\ln \epsilon_{c,0}$ versus $1/T$ for constant stress; 50 MPa and (b) $\ln \epsilon_{c,0}$ versus $\ln \sigma_c$ at 350 °C.

The values for the creep parameters measured under isothermal and constant stress conditions for the 5083 Al alloy are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Creep dependent parameters

Parameter	5083-H116
A_I (-)	1.81×10^8
n_I ($MPa^{4.161}$)	-4.16
Q_I (J/mol)	2.83×10^4
A_{II} (s^{-1})	2.74×10^{-3}
n_{II} ($MPa^{-5.051}$)	5.05
Q_{II} (J/mol)	1.23×10^5

To assess the reliability of these parameters for transient temperature conditions representative of a fire, the creep behavior of the aluminum under non-

uniform heating was determined. This is necessary because the creep process may be dependent on the heating rate of the aluminum. The specimen temperature was increased at a constant rate of 12°C/min, and the evolution of creep strain with increasing temperature and time is shown in Figure 6. The calculated creep strain (using the isothermal creep parameters) is plotted with the experimental creep strain data. Good agreement is observed between the experimental and calculated creep strains, thereby validating the creep parameters for the transient heating conditions that occur in fire.

Figure 6: Transient creep test and simulation at $\sigma = 50$ MPa, and heating rate = 12 °C/min

4.2 Creep Failure in Fire

Failure is defined by two critical events that occur while the compression-loaded aluminum is exposed to fire: (i) initiation of buckling signaled by a reversal to the in-plane distortion response of the plate and (ii) final structural collapse signaled by the sudden and irreversible increase to the in-plane and out-of-plane displacements of the plate. Figure 7 shows the in-plane and out-of-plane displacements of aluminum specimens over the course of fire structural tests performed under low load/low heat flux conditions (Figure 7a) and high load/high heat flux conditions (Figure 7b). The in-plane displacement initially increases due to thermal expansion of the aluminum plate while the out-of-plane displacement is negligible because the plate remains aligned with the load direction.

Figure 7: Failure criterion: (a) initiation of buckling signaled by reversal to the in-plane displacement and (b) total structural collapse indicated by unstable in-plane displacement and out-of-plane buckling.

At some critical time and temperature during the test the in-plane displacement starts to reverse and this is accompanied by a small increase in the out-of-plane displacement. This is identified in Figure 7 as the ‘buckling instability’ point, which signifies the beginning of irreversible plastic buckling of the aluminum plate. The plate initially buckles stably under low load/low heat flux conditions due to the slow creep softening process whereas buckling is unstable under high load/high heat flux conditions due to rapid creep. Unstable buckling is distinguished by the sudden drop in the in-plane displacement and rapid rise in the out-of-plane deflection of the plate. The plate is unable to support the applied load with the onset of unstable buckling, and this point is identified by the ‘buckling collapse’

point in Figure 7. There is a significant difference in the time-to-failure between the initiation of the buckling instability and final collapse of the plate under low heat fluxes and/or low load conditions. However, at high loads and/or high heat fluxes the difference is insignificant because final collapse quickly follows the initial instability of the plate. For each test condition, two times-to-failure are thus established.

The effect of applied compression stress and heat flux on the failure times of the aluminum plate is shown in Figure 8. The heat fluxes of 35 and 50 kW/m² generated maximum temperatures of about 280 and 360°C, which cause significant loss in stiffness and strength of the aluminum. The data points in Figure 8 show the experimental failure times measured in the fire structural test. Figure 8 shows, as expected, that the failure time increase when the compression stress or heat flux is reduced. The reduction is due primarily to a slowing of the creep rate. The curves in Figure 8a and 8b show respectively predictive failure times for the onset of ‘buckling instability’ and ‘final collapse’ using the creep-based fire model. In the model, buckling instability and final collapse were assumed to occur when the creep strain reached 12×10^{-6} and 33×10^{-6} , respectively. These values were obtained from calibration conditions already discussed in Section 2.2. The model provides a good prediction of the failure times at a heat flux of 50 kW/m². Average percent errors in failure time predictions were calculated to be 10 and 15% for ‘buckling instability’ and ‘final collapse’ at this heat flux. At these relatively high heat fluxes (which are more representative of intense fires) the model can almost accurately predict compression failure due to creep.

The creep model can also predict the critical temperatures that correspond to the initiation and final failure of the aluminum plate by buckling. Figure 9 presents comparisons of the measured and calculated temperatures at which buckling instability begins and when the plate finally collapses. The agreement is good. It is envisaged that the model can be used in the fire assessment of compression-loaded aluminum structures. In the use of aluminum in high fire risk structural applications in ships, aircraft and civil infrastructure (e.g. buildings, bridges), it is

important to accurately predict using a robust model the failure time and temperature for different fire scenarios and load conditions.

The model described in the paper is still to be validated on intermediate scale aluminum structures exposed to fire. For these tests, the ratio of heated area to specimen area is significantly larger, thus resulting in higher temperatures for the same heat flux due to lesser conductive losses along specimen edges away from the heat source. The temperatures achieved will be close to the temperatures representative of real fire scenarios.

Figure 8: Effects of heat flux and applied compression stress on the failure times of the aluminum plate. The curves show the theoretical predictions using the creep fire model. (a) Failure defined by initiation of buckling. (b) Failure defined by buckling collapse of the plate.

Figure 9: Comparison of the calculated and measured failure temperatures of the aluminum plate. (a) Failure defined by initiation of buckling. (b) Failure defined by buckling collapse of the plate.

4.3 Fire Structural Response: Composites

The modeling approach for predicting structural failure of laminates was validated by comparing calculated time-to-failure values against experimental failure times for GVE specimens loaded in compression while exposed to one-sided radiant heating. Calculated and experimental failure times for GVE laminates under compression loading are shown in Figure 10. As expected, the failure times increase when the applied stress is reduced.

The model predicts the general trend of increasing failure time with decreasing stress level, although the agreement with the experimental data is (in most cases) not exact. There are several reasons for the inability of the modeling approach to accurately

calculate the failure times under compression. One of them is that the model only provides an approximate calculation of the temperature in the laminate, although highly accurate predictions of the temperature profile is required due to the strong dependency of the failure time on the temperature, especially for compressive failure which occurs in a shorter time. Several assumptions used in the model also affect the accuracy of the failure times, including the assumption that failure does not occur in a progressive fashion, heat-induced delaminations do not affect the failure time, simplified strength-mass loss correlation, and time-dependent creep softening of the polymer matrix and fibres is ignored. Despite the many simplifying assumptions, the modeling approach provides an approximate estimate of the failure times for GVE laminates.

Figure 10: Measured and predicted failure times for laminates tested in compression at 50 kW/m². Experimental is represented by data points while solid lines represent theoretical time-to-failure predictions.

5 Conclusions

A creep-based analytical procedure based on the original work of Maljaars et al. [1] has been used to model the softening, deformation and failure of non-age-hardenable aluminum alloys under combined compression loading and one-sided transient heating by fire. The model can predict the times and temperatures for the onset and final failure of aluminum plate by buckling. The good agreement between the experimental and analytical results shows the model can be applied with confidence to predict buckling failure of aluminum columns when

exposed to high temperature fire. The simplicity of the constitutive model implementation makes it attractive for the design analysis of fire-threatened aluminum structures. However, the validation of the model was limited to a simple aluminum plate structure. For more complex structures, finite element based numerical analysis using the creep model can lead to accurate predictions of the deformation and failure times. The development of a numerical model to assess the structural response of compression loaded aluminum specimens in fire is a subject for further research.

A modeling approach to predict the thermal response, softening and failure of GVE laminates when exposed to fire has been validated. The modeling approach provides an approximation of the temperature rise, softening and failure of the composite laminate when exposed to combined one-sided radiant heating and axial compression. The failure times predicted using the model are approximate, but not exact, due to simplifying assumptions made in the analysis. It is expected that better accuracy in the failure time predictions could be achieved by improved analysis, such as modeling of three-dimensional gas flow, delamination cracking, and creep-induced elasto-plastic flow of the laminate. While the modeling approach only gives approximate estimates of the softening and failure time of the laminate, it provides the foundation for further development of the analysis to improve predictive accuracy.

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